

Real-time Bubble Status of US Stock Market After the 2020 Stock Market Crash

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Abstract

After the 2020 US Stock market crash, the S&P 500 index has increased by 114.5% just within 21 months, from 2237.4 on March 23, 2020, to its all-time high value of 4798.1 on December 30, 2021. Then the S&P 500 index has experienced a series of strong corrects and lost nearly a quarter of its value by October 2022, wiping more than \$10 trillion off market value. In this study, we apply the Log-periodic power law singularity (LPPLS) model to carry out the real-time detection for the recent positive and negative bubble status of the S&P 500 index from April 2020 to December 2022. We find that a series of positive LPPLS confidence indicator clusters of the S&P 500 index have formed from August 2020 to January 2022. The positive LPPLS confidence indicator reaches the global peak value of 26.4% on Nov 30, 2021, which is a rare situation for stock markets, confirming that the price trajectory of S&P 500 index is indeed in a positive bubble regime and the system goes critical and becomes exquisitely sensitive to a small perturbation. Thus, the strong corrections of S&P 500 index from January 2022 stem from the increasingly systemic instability of the stock market itself, while the well-known external shocks, e.g., the decades-high inflation, aggressive monetary policy tightening by the Federal Reserve, and the impact of the Russia/Ukraine war, only serve as sparks. Further, the results show that the long-term LPPLS confidence indicator has better and more stable performance than the short-term LPPLS confidence indicator.

Key Words: Financial bubble and crash, Log-periodic power law singularity (LPPLS), LPPLS confidence indicator

1. Introduction

During the period between February and April in 2020, the US stock market suffered a great crash and the S&P 500 index, one of the most followed stock indexes, dropped from 3386.1 on February 19, 2020, to 2237.4 on March 23, 2020, losing 33.9% of its value. After the 2020 US Stock market crash, the S&P 500 index has increased by 114.5% just within 21 months, from 2237.4 on March 23, 2020, to its all-time high value of 4798.1 on December 30, 2021. Then the S&P 500 index has experienced a series of strong corrects and lost nearly a quarter of its value by October 2022, wiping more than \$10 trillion off market value. In this study, we apply the Log-periodic power law singularity (LPPLS) methodology to conduct the real-time bubble detection and analyze the bubble status of US stock market after the 2020 stock market crash by using the S&P 500 index from April 2020 to December 2022.

In the LPPLS model, a positive (negative) financial bubble is modeled as a process of unsustainably super-exponential growth (decrease) to achieve an infinite return in finite time, forcing a short-lived correction organized according to the symmetry of discrete scale invariance. The LPPLS model captures two distinct characteristics of price trajectory of an asset normally observed in the regime of speculative bubbles: the transient super-exponential growth and the accelerating log-periodic oscillations, to model financial bubble as a process of faster-than-exponential power law growth

punctuated by short-lived corrections. The LPPLS model provides a flexible and quantitative framework for detecting endogenous financial bubbles by analyzing the temporal price series of an asset and has been adopted for the ex-ante diagnosis and postmortem analysis of financial bubbles and crashes in multiple financial markets (Shu, 2019; Shu et al., 2021c, 2021d, 2021b, 2021a; Shu & Zhu, 2020b, 2020a, 2021, 2022; Song et al., 2022).

2. Methods

2.1 The Log-Periodic Power Law Singularity Model

The LPPLS model stems from a risk neutral rational agent with rational expectations and ignoring the arbitrage, dividends, the interest rate, risk aversion, information asymmetry and the market clearing condition. Filimonov and Sornette (2013) proposed the reformed LPPLS formula:

$$\text{LPPLS}(t) \equiv E[\ln p(t)] = A + B(t_c - t)^m + C_1(t_c - t)^m \cos[\omega \ln(t_c - t)] + C_2(t_c - t)^m \sin[\omega \ln(t_c - t)] \quad (1)$$

In Equation (1), $p(t)$ is the observed asset price, A is the expected value of the log-price at the critical time t_c , which is the most probable time for a regime change in a form of a major crash or a great change of growth rate. In a bubble regime, the power parameter m ranges between 0 and 1, ensuring that the price remains finite at t_c , while the expected logarithmic price diverges at t_c .

The LPPLS model consists of three nonlinear parameters (t_c, m, ω) and the four linear parameters (A, B, C_1, C_2). Using the L^2 norm, the sum of squares of residuals of the LPPLS formula can be expressed as:

$$F(t_c, m, \omega, A, B, C_1, C_2) = \sum_{i=1}^N [\ln p(\tau_i) - A - B(t_c - \tau_i)^m - C_1(t_c - \tau_i)^m \cos(\omega \ln(t_c - \tau_i)) - C_2(t_c - \tau_i)^m \sin(\omega \ln(t_c - \tau_i))]^2 \quad (2)$$

where $\tau_1 = t_1$ and $\tau_N = t_2$. The 4 linear parameters (A, B, C_1, C_2) can be analytically solved using the following matrix equations

$$\begin{pmatrix} N & \sum f_i & \sum g_i & \sum h_i \\ \sum f_i & \sum f_i^2 & \sum f_i g_i & \sum f_i h_i \\ \sum g_i & \sum f_i g_i & \sum g_i^2 & \sum g_i h_i \\ \sum h_i & \sum f_i h_i & \sum g_i h_i & \sum h_i^2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \hat{A} \\ \hat{B} \\ \hat{C}_1 \\ \hat{C}_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sum \ln p_i \\ \sum f_i \ln p_i \\ \sum g_i \ln p_i \\ \sum h_i \ln p_i \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The three nonlinear parameters (t_c, m, ω) can be estimated by solving the resulting nonlinear optimization problem:

$$\{\hat{t}_c, \hat{m}, \hat{\omega}\} = \arg \min_{\{t_c, m, \omega\}} F_1(t_c, m, \omega) \quad (4)$$

We used the covariance matrix adaptation evolution strategy to solve this optimization problem.

2.2 LPPLS confidence indicator

The LPPLS confidence indicator is defined as the fraction of fitting windows in which the LPPLS calibrations satisfy the specified filter conditions. It is used to measure sensitivity of observed bubble pattern to the time interval between the end time and the start time in the fitting windows ($dt = t_2 - t_1$) (Sornette et al., 2015). A large value of the LPPLS confidence indicator indicates a more reliable LPPLS pattern. A small value of the indicator signals a possible fragility since the LPPLS pattern is presented in a few fitting windows. This study creates a series of fitting time windows through shrinking the fitting window length from 650 trading days to 30 trading days in steps of 5

trading days for a given fictitious “present” data point t_2 , which is moving from April 1, 2020, to December 30, 2022.

To ensure model rigorousness, the search space is set to (Shu & Zhu, 2020b):

$$m \in [0,1], \omega \in [1, 50], t_c \in \left[t_2, t_2 + \frac{t_2 - t_1}{3} \right], \frac{m|B|}{\omega \sqrt{c_1^2 + c_2^2}} \geq 1 \quad (5)$$

The calibrated LPPLS model is filtered under the following constrains to determine the valid LPPLS fits:

$$m \in [0.01, 0.99], \omega \in [2, 25], t_c \in \left[t_2, t_2 + \frac{t_2 - t_1}{5} \right], \frac{\omega}{2} \ln \left(\frac{t_c - t_1}{t_c - t_2} \right) \geq 2.5, \\ \max \left(\frac{|\hat{p}_t - p_t|}{p_t} \right) \leq 0.20, p_{lomb} \leq \alpha_{sign}, \ln(\hat{p}_t) - \ln(p_t) \sim \text{AR}(1) \quad (6)$$

3. Results

We have conducted the real-time detection for the recent positive and negative bubble status of the S&P 500 index from April 2020 to December 2022. In this study, the data of S&P 500 index comes from Yahoo Finance (<https://finance.yahoo.com/>). Positive bubbles are associated with accelerating growth trends that are susceptible to regime changes in the form of large crashes or volatile sideways plateaus, while negative bubbles are associated with accelerating downward trends that are vulnerable to state change in the form of rallies or volatile sideways plateaus.

Figure 1 shows the daily LPPLS confidence indicator for positive bubbles shown in red and negative bubbles in green (right scale) along with the S&P 500 index in blue (left scale), from 4/1/2020 to 12/30/2022. The positive LPPLS confidence indicator reaches the global peak value of 26.4% on Nov 30, 2021, i.e., 33 out of 125 fitting windows can successfully pass the filters which is a rare situation for stock markets, indicating that the detected LPPLS bubble pattern is very reliable, and the price trajectory of S&P 500 index can be confirmed in a positive speculative bubble regime. The accelerating growth trend of the S&P 500 index is unsustainable. As the positive bubble is maturing, the growth rate is very likely to change because the average state of the system becomes exquisitely sensitive to a small perturbation. Given that the LPPLS model can only detect the endogenous bubbles and crashes, the strong corrections of S&P 500 index starting from January 2022 are endogenous, stemming from the growing instability of the stock market itself, while the well-known external shocks only serve as sparks, such as the decades-high inflation, aggressive monetary policy tightening by the Federal Reserve, and the impact of the Russia/Ukraine war. Interestingly, the date of the all-time high value of 4798.1, i.e., December 30, 2021, falls within the time range of a positive bubble cluster formed from November 11, 2021, to January 14, 2022, during which period the positive LPPLS confidence indicator also reaches the global peak value of 26.4% a month earlier. Further, a cluster of negative bubble can be also observed between June 13 and July 14, 2022, with the peak value of 5.6% on June 21, 2022. In this period, the S&P 500 index research a local rally.

We also study the performance of LPPLS confidence indicator under two-scale fitting window length, by dividing the 125 fitting windows into two subgroups: short-term and long-term. The fitting windows in the short-term time scale subgroup are generated by moving the t_1 towards the t_2 from 200 data points to 30 data points in a step of 5 data points to get 35 fitting windows. Similarly, the length of fitting window is shrunk by moving the t_1 towards the t_2 from 650 data points to 205 data points in a step of 5 data points to generate 90 fitting windows for the long-term time scale subgroup.

Figure 2 and Figure 3 show the LPPLS confidence indicator for positive bubbles in red and negative bubbles in green (right scale) along with the S&P 500 index in blue (left scale) from 4/1/2020 to 12/30/2022 in the long-term time scale and short-term time scale, respectively. In this study, the

long-term LPPLS confidence indicator has better and more stable performance than the short-term LPPLS confidence indicator. Figure 2 presents the distinct cluster of long-term positive confidence indicator from November 11, 2021, to January 12, 2022, with the peak of 36.7% on November 30, 2021, which accurately predict the positive bubble regime change of the S&P 500 index one month later. While the noticeable cluster of the short-term negative confidence indicator in Figure 3 from June 13 to July 14, 2022, with the peak of 20% on June 21, 2022, successfully captures the negative bubble regime change in a short-term time scale.

Figure 1: Daily LPPLS confidence indicator for positive bubbles is shown in red and negative bubbles in green (right scale) along with the S&P 500 index in blue (left scale), from 4/1/2020 to 12/30/2022

Figure 2: Long-term daily LPPLS confidence indicator for positive bubbles is shown in red and negative bubbles in green (right scale) along with the S&P 500 index in blue (left scale), from 4/1/2020 to 12/30/2022.

Figure 3: Short-term daily LPPLS confidence indicator for positive bubbles is shown in red and negative bubbles in green (right scale) along with the S&P 500 index in blue (left scale), from 4/1/2020 to 12/30/2022.

4. Conclusions

We apply the LPPLS model to carry out the real-time detection for the recent positive and negative bubble status of the S&P 500 index from April 2020 to December 2022. We find that a series of positive LPPLS confidence indicator clusters of the S&P 500 index have formed from August 2020 to January 2022. The positive LPPLS confidence indicator reaches the global peak value of 26.4% on Nov 30, 2021, which is a rare situation for stock markets, confirming that the price trajectory of S&P 500 index is indeed in a positive bubble regime and the system goes critical and becomes exquisitely sensitive to a small perturbation. Thus, the strong corrections of S&P 500 index from January 2022 stem from the increasingly systemic instability of the stock market itself, while the well-known external shocks only serve as sparks. Further, the results show that the long-term LPPLS confidence indicator has better and more stable performance than the short-term LPPLS confidence indicator.

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